

ISic0402

Mosaic floor recording works dedicated to Venus

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

mosaic

Object

mosaic

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Lost

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in Syracuse, 11 February 1576 in the square of the no-longer extant S.Margarita, Piazza de Montedoro, an earlier name for Piazza d'Armi, in the vicinity of the ancient Roman forum

Coordinates

37.066805, 15.285582

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Cn(aeus) Octavio(s) A(uli) f(ilius) mini(ster) cohor(tis) bolonar(um)
2. velic(us) Vener(is) Taric(hinae) pavimentum sedi
3. lia fecit aedemque reficiend(am) coir(avit)

Apparatus

Text of Gaggiotti 2002

Translation (en)

Cnaeus Octavius, son of Aulus, officer and administrator of the company of fishmongers made the pavement and benches and saw to the restoration of the temple of Venus Tarichina (Venus of the Saltworks)

Commentary

The mosaic is lost, and modern readings are dependent upon an unsatisfactory

text recorded in the antiquarian tradition

Digital identifiers:

TM 491613

EDCS 21900443

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